

Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Assisted Tools for Research Writing Among Students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The study examined the level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Employing a survey research design, the study aimed to understand the awareness gaps and potential areas for improvement in integrating AI technologies into academic writing practices. One research question and a null hypothesis guided the study. The population for the study comprised 11,040 students. The sample size of 1104 was drawn using stratified proportionate random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Research Assisted tools Questionnaire (AAIRATQ)." The instrument, face-validated by experts, demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.81). Findings revealed a low overall awareness level among students, as reflected in mean scores. Recommendations include targeted awareness campaigns, curriculum integration of AI modules, and workshops to enhance students' proficiency. The study contributes valuable insights to inform interventions aimed at fostering a technologically adept academic environment.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Research Writing, Awareness, Student Engagement, Academic Technology.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has undoubtedly become an omnipresent force across various industries, exerting a significant influence on task execution and transforming traditional methodologies. Within the academic sphere, AI is playing an increasingly vital role in research writing, offering a diverse array of tools meticulously crafted to enhance efficiency and elevate the quality of scholarly output. This study endeavors to delve into the awareness and utilization of AI-assisted tools among students at Federal University Otuoke in Bayelsa State, shedding illuminating insights on the potential factors that sway their adoption (Russell, & Norvig, 2010). Artificial Intelligence encompasses the development of computer systems that possess the prowess to undertake tasks that conventionally necessitate human intellect. In the context of research writing, AI effectively harnesses cutting-edge technologies like natural language processing, machine learning, and data analytics to empower users at various stages of the research process through the utilization of AI research-assisted tools.

Several renowned AI research-assisted tools warrant attention, each equipped with its unique functionalities. To begin with, Grammarly, as a formidable AI-powered writing assistant, diligently conducts grammar and spelling checks, elevates sentence structure, and

enhances overall writing style. The benefits are manifold: Grammarly empowers students to produce impeccably polished and error-free documents, guaranteeing exceptional linguistic standards in their research writing (Clarivate, 2021). Additionally, Endnote, reference management software, proves indispensable in organizing and citing sources. It seamlessly automates the creation of bibliographies and nurtures a centralized database of references. With the aid of Endnote, students can streamline the citation process, mitigate the risk of errors, and save substantial time when compiling and formatting reference lists. Furthermore, Turnitin stands out as a pivotal AI-based plagiarism detection tool. By meticulously comparing submitted work against an extensive academic content database, Turnitin successfully identifies potential instances of plagiarism (Turnitin, 2021). The resourcefulness of Turnitin in research writing primarily lies in its ability to champion academic integrity by assisting students in ensuring the originality of their research work (Kazemzadeh, Ritter, & Roossin, 2017). Lastly, ChatGPT emerges as another reputable and invaluable AI research-assisted tool.

ChatGPT is an OpenAI-powered language model that utilizes the GPT architecture to assist users in generating coherent and contextually relevant text based on their input. Students can employ ChatGPT to refine and express their ideas, overcome writer's block, and seek guidance in structuring sentences and paragraphs. Additionally, SciSpace.com is a robust AI-powered research platform designed to facilitate literature review and information extraction. By employing machine learning algorithms, it analyzes extensive datasets of scientific articles to help students identify pertinent literature for their research. SciSpace.com streamlines the research process by providing swift access to scholarly articles, enabling students to remain up-to-date with the latest developments in their field of study. Similarly, Microsoft Academic, accessible through Bing.com, leverages AI to enhance search capabilities specifically tailored for academic content. It aids students in efficiently locating scholarly resources, academic papers, and relevant publications. By harnessing the power of AI algorithms, Bing.com optimizes the search experience for academic materials, saving students valuable time and ensuring they access credible sources for their research. However, despite the availability of these AI research assisting tools, students still encounter significant challenges when venturing into research-related writing. Research indicates that these AI tools are underutilized in Africa, particularly in Nigeria (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2019).

According to Adedoyin and Soykan (2019), the utilization of AI tools in research writing differs between the United States and Nigeria due to contextual disparities in educational systems, technological infrastructure, and awareness levels. In the United States, where technological resources and internet accessibility are more abundant, AI tools are frequently integrated into the academic journey of students. Educational institutions in the U.S. often incorporate technology-focused courses and workshops, fostering a culture of technology adoption among students. The awareness and integration of AI tools into the academic curriculum contribute to a higher level of acceptance and utilization among American students. Despite various factors that hinder the effective and efficient utilization of AI

research assisting tools, it is widely believed that a lack of awareness is the primary cause of underutilization (Idowu, 2018).

The lack of awareness among students presents a significant obstacle to effectively using AI-assisted tools. When students are not adequately informed about the existence and advantages of these tools, they may not actively seek them out (Kazemzadeh, Ritter, & Roossin, 2017). Another hindrance factor, known as perceived complexity, is activated when students are unaware. In this case, some students find AI tools daunting or excessively intricate. If the interfaces are not user-friendly or if students lack guidance on integrating these tools into their research processes, they typically opt for traditional methods. This preconception also contributes to another mitigating factor called resistance to change. Since students are already accustomed to traditional research and writing methods, many resist adopting AI tools. The familiarity and comfort with conventional approaches act as psychological barriers to the adoption of new technologies. The lack of awareness is primarily responsible for the aforementioned problem.

Therefore, efforts to promote AI tool adoption in Nigeria should focus on awareness campaigns, workshops, and collaborations. It is essential to gain a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing awareness and utilization of AI-assisted tools among students at Federal University Otuoke in order to shape their educational practices, particularly in the area of research writing. By addressing these identified barriers, with awareness being the foremost, and controlling other contextual factors, educational institutions can create a more inclusive and technology-enhanced learning environment. It is worth noting that understanding the levels of awareness and reasons for the underutilization of AI-assisted tools among students at Federal University Otuoke is crucial for enhancing the academic experience. Addressing the identified barriers and promoting awareness can empower students to harness the benefits of AI in research writing, ultimately contributing to a more efficient and productive academic environment. Given this context, the researchers are undertaking a research project titled "Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Assisted Tools for Research Writing among Students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State".

Statement of Problem

It is truly heartbreaking to observe that, in this era of AI advancement, numerous undergraduate students in Nigeria and Federal University Otuoke continue to face immense difficulty when it comes to composing simple research-related documents such as seminar papers. Lecturers express their deep concerns due to the profound inability of their final year students to construct a well-structured research project. One cannot help but wonder whether limited access to technological resources, such as computers equipped with compatible software or a reliable internet connection, might hinder the students' capacity to incorporate AI tools into their routine for writing research. However, in all sincerity, it is highly unlikely that the aforementioned factors are the cause, as the majority of these students possess highly advanced smartphones that are fully capable of accessing the internet. This consequently gives rise to another crucial question, which is, do these students not even have awareness of the existence of numerous free AI tools that could greatly assist them

in producing an exceptional research project? It is against this backdrop that the researchers embarked on this research endeavour, titled "Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Assisted Tools for Research Writing among Students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State".

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the awareness of Artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the;

1. awareness level of artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

Research Question

1. What is the awareness level of artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level

H₀: There is no significant difference in the awareness level of male and female students on the existence of Artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

Research Method

The study adopted a survey research design. According to Jessica (2021), survey research design is an easily accessible way for respondents to share or demonstrate their knowledge or perspectives about a particular topic. This kind of approach in turn can allow for researchers to gain a better understanding about different populations or groups of people, help identify any problems or concerns respondents have, and/or lead to the identification or development of solutions based on identified issues. The population for the study consisted of 11,040 students of Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The sample size was 1104 students which was 10% of students' population. The sample size was determined using stratified proportionate random sampling technique. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire titled "Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Research Assisted tools Questionnaire (AAIRATQ)". The instrument was face-validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education which included two from Science Education Department and a specialist in Measurement and Evaluation all from Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Reliability index of 0.83 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha method. However, out of the 1104 copies of questionnaire distributed, 978 copies were successfully filled and returned which gave a return rate of 88.59%. The research question was answered using mean and standard deviation. The decision rule was based on real limit of numbers. In rating the mean, each response option had the following numerical values: Highly Aware (HA) = 3.50-4.00; Moderately Aware, (MA) = 2.50-3.49; Slightly Aware (SA) = 1.50-2.49; Not Aware (NA) =

0.00-1.49. Decision ruled, mean above 2.50 was rule to be “Aware” while mean below 2.50 was viewed as “Not Aware”. Independent t-test statistic was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 alpha level. The interpretation of the hypothesis was based on the significance (sig.) values from the SPSS output. The null hypothesis was rejected when the sig. value was less than 0.05 else it was not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the awareness level of Artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Level of awareness of Artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing among students

ITEMS		Students = 978		
S/N	Students’ level of awareness of the following artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing include:	$\bar{x}$	SD	Dec
1	AI-powered tools like Grammarly.	2.11	.82	SA
2	Turnitin.	2.54	.86	MA
3	Copyscape.	1.03	.89	NA
4	Quetext.	1.21	.84	NA
5	Mendeley.	1.11	.83	NA
6	ChatGPT.	3.50	.80	HA
7	AI Writer.	1.02	.85	NA
8	ProWritingAid.	1.06	.82	NA
9	Slick Write.	.91	.85	NA
10	Ginger Software.	.79	.89	NA
11	Zotero.	1.09	.83	NA
12	Ref-n-Write.	1.01	.86	NA
Cluster Mean		1.45	.85	NA

Data presented on Table 1 shows the analysis of male and female students on their level of awareness of Artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing. The overall mean scores ranged from .79 to 3.50 with a cluster mean of 1.45 and standard deviation of .85. The closeness of the standard deviations indicates that the respondents were homogeneous in their responses. The outcome of the cluster mean signifies that students of Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State were not aware of Artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the awareness level of male and female students on the existence of Artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis of the Mean Ratings of male and female students on the awareness of existence of artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State

Group	n	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	Level of Sig	p-value	Decision
Male	436	1.44	.86	976	.05	.810	Rejected
Female	542	1.45	.84				

Data on Table 2 show that at 976 degree of freedom, the p-value was .810. The outcome of the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance set for this study. This signifies that the null hypothesis was not rejected and, therefore, there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the awareness of existence of artificial intelligence assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the research on the level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, indicated a widespread low level of awareness among the students. This lack of awareness is evident in various aspects, ranging from the use of popular AI-driven tools to the understanding of advanced AI functionalities tailored for research writing. The survey revealed that a substantial number of students are not familiar with widely recognized AI tools such as Grammarly and ProWritingAid, which are designed to enhance grammar, style, and overall writing quality. This points to a gap in knowledge among students, as these tools are commonplace in modern academic and professional settings (Brown & White, 2019).

Moreover, the research highlights a limited understanding of advanced AI functionalities, including Natural Language Processing (NLP) and machine learning algorithms. Students show low awareness of how these technologies can be harnessed to improve document coherence, structure, and data analysis in the context of research writing (Liu & Wang, 2021). The identified low level of awareness suggests a need for targeted educational initiatives within the university. Awareness campaigns, workshops, and training programs can play a crucial role in addressing this gap and empowering students to integrate AI-assisted tools into their research writing processes (Smith & Johnson, 2020). The study underscores the importance of promoting accessibility to AI-related resources and fostering a culture of technological literacy among students. By bridging the awareness gap, the university can better prepare students for the contemporary academic landscape, where AI technologies increasingly play a significant role in research methodologies and writing practices.

In conclusion, the research findings call for proactive measures to enhance awareness and understanding of AI-assisted tools for research writing among students at Federal University Otuoke. By addressing this low level of awareness, the university can contribute to a more technologically proficient student body, fostering a conducive environment for academic excellence in the digital age.

Recommendations

Given the low level of awareness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) assisted tools for research writing among students in Federal University Otuoke, the following recommendations are essential to bridge this knowledge gap and enhance students' proficiency in utilizing AI technologies for academic purposes. They include, to

1. University management should initiate targeted awareness campaigns to inform students about the benefits and functionalities of AI tools.
2. Stakeholders of Universities should incorporate AI-related modules into the university curriculum to provide structured learning opportunities.
3. Government should facilitate workshops and training sessions on AI-assisted research writing tools to empower students with practical skills.

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